

An ecological study of the Epidemiology of Asthma in Spain: A 12-year time-series study

Marta Burches-Feliciano ¹, Enrique Burches ^{1,*}, Javier Guillem Saiz ², Carmen Saiz Sánchez ³

¹ Allergy Department, ALERGOCONTROL SLP, Valencia, Spain.

² Universidad Europea de Valencia, Valencia, Spain.

³ Public Health Department, Faculty of Medicine, Universitat de Valencia, Valencia, Spain.

*. **Corresponding author:** Enrique Burches, Alergocontrol SLP, Valencia, Spain. Phone: 0034963524046. E-mail: eburchesbaixauli@gmail.com.

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Abstract

Background: Asthma is one of the most common causes of chronic disease, and its incidence has been predicted to be rising for years. Ecological studies with aggregated data, taking into consideration social and economic elements, are interesting because they are limited, especially in the adult population.

Methods: An ecological cross-sectional observational study was carried out utilizing anonymous aggregated data from the National Health Survey. The data used are from 2006, 2011, 2014, and 2017 (a 12-year period). Descriptive statistics on the evolution of asthma prevalence and the elements (social, demographic, and economic) that may be connected were gathered.

Results: Asthma, one of the leading causes of chronic disease, has not increased in recent years. As we can see from the sequential trends, asthma rates have stayed steady over the last 12 years. Asthma prevalence in Spain increased from 4.45% in 2006 to 4.68% in 2017.

Conclusion: We have quantitative data demonstrating the regularity of asthma measurement points across 12 years and the greater prevalence linked to social variables. The asthma time series does not show a steady climb but rather a stabilization of the statistics over 12 years, with a drop in the median age sketching a "V" shape.

Keywords: Asthma, Epidemiology, Prevalence, Multivariate analysis, Social factors, Spain

Introduction

Asthma illnesses are among the most common causes of chronic pathology, and they place an additional and growing load on healthcare costs (1-3). Asthma is currently believed to be a disorder that is expanding rapidly, affecting a considerable proportion of the population, and appearing mostly in developed countries with Western lifestyles (4).

It is also assumed that pollution will have a significant impact. Furthermore, multiple review publications emphasize the role of climate change and global warming in allergy and asthma development (5, 6). They would influence physical parameters like air pressure, rainfall, and environmental temperature, as

well as biological factors like plant pollen production. All of this would have an impact on the target organs involved in allergy and asthma pathophysiology (7).

However, when we look for quantifiable proof of all of these claims, we discover that epidemiological data on asthma in our nation are quite limited in the general Spanish population (8). Normally, we have unrepresentative samples of people who visited the doctor with the suspicion of having asthma (9). Furthermore, there are no ecological studies that use aggregated data (10, 11), and it is worth noting that research on asthma prevalence in relation to social and economic determinants is limited, particularly in the adult population.

Materials and methods

Type of study

An ecological cross-sectional observational analysis was carried out utilizing primarily anonymised aggregated data from the National Health Survey, which are available to the public on both the Ministry of Health and the National Statistics Institute's websites (12-14).

Data sources: The National Health Survey

Data were collected from the National Health Surveys and the National Statistics Institute. This is a cross-sectional, population-based study. The study population and information sources were based on data from 2006, 2011, 2014, and 2017. These are population-based surveys conducted at home with personal interviews and a standardized questionnaire. The reference population is 16 years old or older, not institutionalised, and lives in Spain (12-14).

The selected data is from 2017. It was decided to exclude data from Spain's most recent National Health Survey, which was conducted in 2020, because the results (divided into two periods by the pandemic) were incompatible with the historical series, and indicators reflected behaviors that could have changed as a result of the interviewees' circumstances.

Statistical analysis

First, a descriptive analysis of the qualifying samples was conducted. Using the data sources mentioned in previous sections and the years 2006, 2011, 2014, and 2017, we obtained data on asthma pathology and its involvement based on specific conditions: gender, age, and population type; gender, age, and level of education; and gender, age, and economic social class. The data was cleaned such that it could be used statistically.

All statistical analyses were conducted with the statistical tool R version 1.4.2 and Microsoft Excel version 16.0 (Microsoft Corporation). Source: [Office.microsoft.com/excel](https://office.microsoft.com/excel).

Ross Ihaka and Robert Gentleman (15) invented R, a statistical analysis and graphics system. R is a versatile programming language geared for computational statistics, data analysis, and graphics development. We used the following packages in R:

-Rcmdr (RCommander) and RcmdrMisc (RCommander):

Statistics, Summaries (numeric summary, normality test, correlation test), Means (Single-samples t-test, Independent samples t-test, one-way ANOVA), variances

(Test F, test de Bartlett, test de Levene), nonparametric tests, Dimensional analysis, fit models (k-means), Graphs.

-Plot, Biplot, Library Cluster, Library Factomines

It was carried out:

The selection of variables for statistical analysis, both sanitary (for example, prevalence data, which is the proportion of cases in a community that exhibit a specific feature or condition) and other types (social, demographic, and economic). Although it is not possible to attribute the use of dependent and independent variables in observational studies as it is in experimental studies, we can consider that in our work, some factors such as age, gender, economic and social situation may reflect changes in the outcome of allergy prevalence, which could be considered a dependent variable.

1. Descriptive statistics on the progression of asthma prevalence during the previous 12 years. According to age categories (15-24, 25-44, 35-44, 45-64, 65-74, and over 75 years) and gender.
2. Descriptive statistics on the evolution of asthma prevalence by population type, previous age, and gender group. By population type (less than 10,000, 10,000-50,000, 50,000-100,000, 100,000-400,000, and more than 400,000).
3. Descriptive statistics on the prevalence of asthma by level of study (without studies, first grade, second grade 1, second grade 2, and third grade).
4. Descriptive statistics on the prevalence of allergy according to the economic level (I, II, III, IV, V and VI; I being the highest and VI the lowest) (16).

In each scenario, we performed:

- Descriptive statistics include measurements of central location (mean and median), dispersion (standard deviation, variance, coefficient of variation), and distribution (ranges, maximum and minimum values, skewness and kurtosis).

- Normality was studied using the Shapiro-Wilk test, homocedasticity was assessed using the Barlett and Levene tests, and significance was verified using the Student and Welch tests.

- Descriptive statistics were converted into tables and graphs:

- Tables comparing percentages of prevalence among groups (age, gender, population type, education level, and economic status).
- Tables containing summary parameters from descriptive statistics.

- Diagram of lines with time series based on the categories mentioned.
- Diagrams comparing percentages of prevalence between groupings (age, gender, population type, education level, and economic level).

- Multivariate representation:

Given the data's complexity and size, we performed multivariate analysis (17). These are statistical methods that examine data sets containing multiple measurable variables at the same time. They provide a better grasp of the topic under investigation by acquiring data that univariate and bivariate approaches cannot. Cluster analysis is a multivariate technique that classifies items by constructing groups/clusters that are as homogeneous as feasible within themselves while being heterogeneous with one another.

K-means clustering, a non-hierarchical method, is the most often used unsupervised machine learning algorithm for partitioning a given data set into k groups (i.e., clusters), where k indicates the number of groups pre-specified by the analyst. It divides things into numerous groups (clusters) so that objects within the same cluster are as similar as possible (high intra-class similarity), while objects from different clusters are as dissimilar as possible (low inter-class similarity). In k -means clustering, each cluster is represented by its center (i.e., centroid), which is the average of the points assigned to the cluster. We plot the curve based on the number of clusters k . Partitioning approaches, such as k -means clustering, enable users to define the number of clusters to be created with a single function (`fviz_nbclust`).

Results

Descriptive statistics on the evolution of asthma prevalence over 12 years

The results were collected during a period of time from 2006 to 2017, with subsequent measurements taken in 2006, 2011, 2014, and 2017. Table 1 shows the progression of asthma prevalence in Spain from 2006 to 2017, both in total for both sexes and separately in males and females, including age groups and data for each year of measurement.

Table 1 provides a time trend of the average prevalence of asthma from 2006 to 2017. As we can see from the subsequent changes, the data for doctor-diagnosed asthma have remained constant over the last 12 years: asthma from 2006 to 2017 ranged from 4.45% to 4.68%. The student's T -test between the first and last years of measurement is not significant (p -value = 0.894).

Furthermore, as shown in Table 1, if we look at the average over the last 12 years in the general population, the increase in asthma is primarily apparent in older people and women. Table 1 shows that the prevalence of asthma in the population over 75 years of age was 7.77% in 2006 and 6.51% in 2017. In 2006, the male population reached 8.94%. In females, it is less evident, but it reaches a high of 7% in 2006. In 2006, males aged 65 to 74 had rises of up to 9%. Figures of 6% are attained in populations over 75 years of age, compared to 3% in males aged 45-54 and 55-64 years of age.

The higher incidence in elderly populations is noticeable, as is the regularity of measurement points over the course of 12 years. There is a noticeable increase in the population over 75 years old, both in total and in men and women, as well as a decrease in the 45-54 age range. This image shocks us because it has always been stated that asthma is a chronic disease that should be managed in a gradual rise over time rather than with bumps. The asthma time series indicates a stabilization of the figures compared to 12 years ago, with a fall in the middle ages sketching a "V".

Descriptive statistics of the prevalence of allergy according to level of education

If we consider the levels of studies as follows: no studies, first degree, second degree first cycle, second degree second cycle, and third degree, we can see in Figure 2 and Table 2B that asthma values are higher in people with lower levels, both in total and when separated by gender.

The quantitative data in Table 2B show higher levels of asthma in the lower levels compared to the higher levels. The difference in prevalence between the lowest and greatest educational levels is statistically significant. Because Bartlett's test indicated no homoscedasticity ($F = 0,12033$, p -value = 0,004192), we used the Welch test, which showed extremely clear significance (p -value = 0.000575).

Descriptive statistics of the prevalence of allergy according to economic level

To characterize the economic level, we used the occupational social class, which obtains the social class of the individual who works or has worked, as well as the main breadwinner, and selects the most privileged of these two, grouping into social classes I, II, and III (more privileged) and IV, V, and VI (less privileged) according to that adapted for the National Health Survey (16).

Table 1. Evolution of the prevalence of asthma in Spain from 2006 to 2017

		2006	2011	2014	2017	Average
years old						
Both genders	Total	4,45	4,08	4,37	4,68	4,39259337
	15-24	5,03	4,72	3,95	5,22	4,72998834
	25-34	4,47	4,49	4,80	5,31	4,76632634
	35-44	2,97	4,03	4,71	4,19	3,97765378
	45-54	3,35	2,97	3,02	3,98	3,33002915
	55-64	4,06	3,38	4,19	3,78	3,85338891
	65-74	5,68	4,33	5,06	4,79	4,96207036
	75 & more	7,77	5,28	5,42	6,51	6,24429561
Males	Total	3,93	3,38	3,90	3,74	3,73626227
	15-24	4,72	4,67	3,81	3,45	4,16250072
	25-34	3,79	3,61	5,11	4,31	4,20452891
	35-44	2,29	4,12	3,91	4,36	3,66930745
	45-54	2,67	1,80	2,46	2,70	2,41027939
	55-64	3,61	2,28	2,93	2,65	2,86881707
	65-74	5,14	3,18	4,15	4,15	4,15679707
	75 & more	8,94	4,45	6,22	5,38	6,24539774
Females	Total	4,94	4,75	4,82	5,57	5,01826246
	15-24	5,35	4,76	4,10	7,08	5,32381508
	25-34	5,20	5,40	4,49	6,30	5,34631206
	35-44	3,68	3,95	5,54	4,02	4,29739218
	45-54	4,03	4,12	3,58	5,25	4,24652457
	55-64	4,48	4,42	5,40	4,86	4,78941055
	65-74	6,09	5,32	5,86	5,36	5,65642652
	75 & more	6,94	5,82	4,89	7,25	6,22639077

Time series of the average of prevalence by total figures for both genders and separately in males and females, adding the age groups and showing the data for each of the years of measurement.

Table 2. Evolution of the prevalence of asthma in Spain from 2006 to 2017 respect to the type of population (number of inhabitants) (A), education level (B) and economic level (C), showing the data for each of the years of measurement

	2006	2001	2014	2017
Total average	4,45	4,08	4,37	4,68
A				
No. inhabitants				
Until 10000	4,97	4,17	4,24	4,58
10000 - 50000	4,06	4,56	4,42	4,81
50001 - 100000	4,33	3,45	4,13	4,81
100000 - 400000	4,98	4,50	4,62	4,64
400000 & more	3,76	3,18	4,31	4,54
B				
Education level				
No studies	7,80	6,22	5,71	7,33
First level	4,61	4,12	4,58	4,70
Second level 1	4,43	3,87	4,28	4,19
Second level 2	3,64	3,73	4,11	4,23
Third level	3,33	3,55	3,88	4,63
C				
Economic level				
I	2,77	2,93	3,46	4,00
II	3,89	3,51	4,03	4,25
III	4,05	3,35	4,76	4,22
IV	4,77	3,89	4,41	4,91
V	5,75	4,59	4,38	5,08
VI	4,76	4,94	4,67	4,67

The quantitative data reflects with higher levels of asthma in the lower educational levels compared to the higher educational levels. Moreover, there are higher levels of asthma in the lower income levels compared to the higher income levels. We have not detected significant differences in asthmatics according to population.

Table 3. Descriptive statistics of the evolution of the prevalence of asthma in the time series, with respect to the type of population (A), education level (B) and economic level (C)

	Average	Standard error	Median	Standard deviation	Variance	Kurtosis	Swkness
A Prevalence of asthma: type of population							
Until 10000	4.48992151	0.18449105	4.40923217	0.36898214	0.13614779	1.14113948	-
10000-50000	4.48992251	0.15641062	4.48970312	0.31282125	0.09785713	0.74494977	-
50000-100000	4.48992251	0.28244391	4.23053733	0.56488781	0.31909824	1.01488799	-
100000-400000	4.48992251	0.10182832	4.63279441	0.20365664	0.04147603	2.60824762	-
400000 & more	4.48992251	0.30337167	4.03834563	0.60674333	0.36813747	1.52522146	-
B Prevalence of asthma : education level							
No studies	6.76673981	0.48429463	6.77858373	0.96858927	0.93816517	3.63566822	-
First level	4.50079811	0.13064974	4.59592548	0.26129947	0.06827741	3.41636782	-
Second level 1	4.19256664	0.11847106	4.23574115	0.23694212	0.05614157	1.46031217	-
Second level 2	3.92703535	0.14175281	3.91901874	0.28350562	0.08037543	4.70060052	-
Third level	3.84648349	0.28385791	3.71673821	0.56771579	0.32230122	0.97410696	-
C Prevalence of asthma : economic level							
I	3.29126666	0.27940363	3.19448081	0.55880734	0.31226562	1.57343835	-
II	3.91992727	0.15635522	3.96170751	0.31271045	0.09778782	0.91961863	-
III	4.09566452	0.29130076	4.13706712	0.58260133	0.33942431	1.16844013	-
IV	4.49534874	0.22887698	4.59212417	0.45775383	0.20953855	0.33927442	-
V	4.95083583	0.30432331	4.83461765	0.60864662	0.37045077	0.63878681	-
VI	4.76331863	0.06344571	4.71858764	0.12689132	0.01610145	1.51178462	-

The descriptive statistics of the evolution of the prevalence of asthma reflects a centered distribution in which the median follows values similar to the mean, a fact that is corroborated by both the kurtosis and the skewness coefficient. The skewness coefficient is moderately negative or positive for the most part, and the kurtosis follows a similar pattern with slightly higher values. The dispersion of the sample according to the standard deviation is around 5-15 % in most groups.

Figure 1. Line diagram of the average prevalence of asthma in Spain from 2006 to 2017 respect to the age of population by total figures for both sexes, and separately in males and females. The percentage prevalence is expressed in ordinates and in abscissas the age of population by total figures for both genders, and separately in males and females. Prevalence is also expressed numerically on the graph.

Figure 2. The average prevalence of asthma in the time series, expressing in ordinates the percentage of prevalence and in abscissas the different groups according to the level of studies and differentiating in total figures for both genders and separately in males and females. Prevalence is also expressed numerically on the graph.

Figure 3. The average prevalence of asthma in the time series, expressing in ordinates the percentage of prevalence and in abscissas the different groups according to the economic level and differentiating in total in total figures for both genders and separately in males and females. Prevalence is also expressed numerically on the graph.

Figure 3 and the quantitative data in Table 2C show higher levels of asthma in lower income levels compared to higher income levels. There is roughly a two-point gap between levels V and VI in terms of the prevalence of high levels. The difference in prevalence between the lowest and highest socioeconomic levels is statistically significant. Because Barlett's test indicated homoscedasticity ($F = 0.83587$, $p\text{-value} = 0.6709$), we used Student's test, which showed extremely obvious significance with $p\text{-value} = 0.00082$.

Descriptive statistics of the prevalence of asthma with respect to the type of population

Table 2A shows the evolution of asthma prevalence when age and gender are taken into account, as well as the type of population in terms of population size (less than 10,000 inhabitants, 10,000 to 50,000 inhabitants, 50,000 to 100,000 inhabitants, 100,000 to 400,000 inhabitants, and more than 400,000 inhabitants).

We found no significant differences in the total number of male and female asthmatics based on population. Table 3A shows that the lowest statistics at the overall level (both gender) relate to populations of more than 400,000 inhabitants (3.95%), while populations of up to 10,000 inhabitants have 4.48%. The pattern does not change during the years of assessment (Table 2A), and there are no significant variations between populations, regardless of population size. We could not find any data from studies that linked asthma to the number of people in the population center where the patient lived.

The descriptive statistics of the evolution of asthma prevalence are provided in Table 3 ABC, and they reveal a centered distribution with the median following values similar to the mean, as confirmed by both the kurtosis and the skewness coefficient. The skewness coefficient is mostly negative or positive, while the kurtosis has a similar pattern with slightly greater values. In most groups, the sample dispersion in terms of standard deviation is between 5 and 15%. The Shapiro-Wilk normality test demonstrates that the results follow a normal distribution.

We then performed multivariate analysis utilizing cluster analysis. This research used the k-means and R clusplot algorithms to group data into clusters. K-means clustering, a non-jerarquic method, is the most widely used unsupervised machine learning technique for splitting a data set into k groups (i.e., clusters). Partitioning approaches, such as k-means clustering, find and visualize the best number of clusters using various methods, and users must choose the number of clusters to be formed (single R function: fviz_nbclust).

We can observe which cluster each of the age and gender niches are clustered in (using the mean of each throughout the span of years measured, as shown in Table 1), as well as their corresponding allergy prevalence figures. The variables are assigned in each of the clusters referred to, in the order of the age groups in Table 1 (3 clusters, with a number of components of 15, 6, and 3 respectively, numbered 1 2 3 and integrating the mean asthma prevalence groups by age and both genders in table 1, ordered in vector clustering

as listed in the column labelled average in table 1 from top to bottom).

Clustering vector: 1 1 1 1 2 1 1 3 1 1 1 1 2 2
1 3 1 3 3 1 1 1 3 3

Cluster 2 contains males aged 45-54 years and 55-64 years, who have the lowest prevalence, as well as the 45-54 age range for both sexes, which has the lowest prevalence within this total group. Cluster 3 includes elderly groups and women aged 15-24/25-34, who have the highest incidence.

Discussion

It is well known that there is little current data on asthma in adults. Although the information on the true prevalence of asthma is hampered by a paucity of data, it was determined that there is a real increase in asthma in adults, posing a severe global public health concern. To increase illness prevention outcomes, educational efforts should be targeted at patients and their families. Public health officials should lobby for adequate resources to diagnose, regulate, treat, and prevent asthma diseases (2,3).

The results to be highlighted are, first, as we can see from the subsequent changes, the data for asthma have remained stable over the last 12 years: in Spain, the prevalence of asthma from 2006 to 2017 increased from 4.45% to 4.68%. If we look at the average over the last 12 years in the general population, the increase in asthma is primarily apparent in older people and women.

It is well understood that a small number of studies using different approaches or insufficient data make calculating asthma prevalence difficult. According to the research, asthma is a widespread chronic condition with the potential to increase in prevalence. However, little is understood regarding its distribution and determinants. The European Community Respiratory Health Survey (18) is a multicenter study that examines the prevalence, causes, and management of asthma. It describes how asthma symptoms vary across Europe. A screening questionnaire, which included questions about the 12-month prevalence of asthma symptoms, was provided to representative samples of men and women aged 20 to 44 years in 48 sites, primarily in Western Europe. The average response rate to the questionnaire was 75%. The average prevalence of asthma was 5.2% (range: 1.2-13%). The following question was asked: "Have you had an asthma attack in the past 12 months?". Females exhibited a higher prevalence of asthma than males, and wheeze prevalence was inversely proportional to age. The prevalence of all symptoms varied significantly. The frequency of asthma varied greatly by geography.

Although values were usually lowest in northern, central, and southern Europe, and highest in the British Isles, there were significant differences within some countries. Centers with a high incidence of asthma attacks also had high rates of nasal allergies. Asthma drugs were more commonly used in areas with more frequent wheeze and asthma symptoms. In most centers in the Netherlands, Sweden, and the United Kingdom, more than 80% of people with asthma were using asthma drugs. In Italy, France, and Spain, the rate was typically lower than 70%. These data provide the best evidence to date that spatial disparities in asthma prevalence exist, are significant, and are not the result of non-comparable methodologies. It was established that geographic variations in asthma prevalence were most likely caused by environmental variables.

When we compare the results of other studies, we discover that there are no references in the literature on the epidemiology of asthma in relation to factors such as type of population, educational level, or labor factors such as type of occupation and type of working day, though there are some that deal with asthma from a socioeconomic standpoint. As a result of national health surveys, we were unable to locate any publications that investigated the association between adult allergies and socioeconomic characteristics (such as educational level, social class, or income level) in the general population. It would be fascinating to compare our findings to those of other national health surveys from different nations. Although there are no epidemiological research on the entire population, we did find studies on certain population groups, such as military-age males (19), schoolchildren of various levels, and university students (20).

In our contribution, we linked asthma patients' educational levels to their pathology. In total figures for both sexes, the group with no education comprises 6.76% and the group with the greatest level of education 3.84%, corresponding to the highest and lowest percentages. The discrepancy is higher among women, with 7.17% having no education and 4.15% having the greatest level.

If we consider the degree of research (using the aforementioned classification), we can see that the group with no studies has a greater overall prevalence: 7.80% in 2006, 6.62% in 2011, and 7.33% in 2017. Especially among the higher-level group, which ranged from 3.33% in 2006 to 3.55% in 2011, 3.88% in 2014, and 4.63% in 2017. There is a significant increase in the ignorant population, both sexes included.

Between 1985 and 1996/97, an 11-year community cohort research in Norway with 2819 subjects aged 15-70 years looked at the cumulative incidence of asthma and respiratory symptoms by educational level (primary, secondary, and university). The incidence of

all respiratory problems decreased as education level increased (20).

The role of socioeconomic position in the development of asthma is uncertain, with some research pointing to lower risks and others to higher risks. Among the few research we located on the subject, a systematic examination of past publications linking asthma disease to socioeconomic characteristics reveals that a lower social class was associated with a higher frequency of asthma in 63% of the studies (21). Our findings are partly similar; higher economic levels reveal lower asthma prevalence (2.11% in 2006, 2.93% in 2011, 3.46% in 2014, and 4% in 2017).

Unlike adults, there is concern about the global prevalence of pediatric asthma. There were significant differences in the prevalence of asthma symptoms and allergy illnesses around the world. Although asthma, rhinitis, and eczema symptoms are less common in underdeveloped countries, some have unusually high rates of these illnesses and proportionally more severe symptoms. The International Study of Asthma and Allergy in Childhood (ISAAC phase III) found significant differences among the areas investigated, with no consistent regional trend (22). Asthma, rhinitis, and eczema symptoms are more common in some high-income Western countries, such as the United Kingdom, New Zealand, and Australia, but not in others, such as Spain (22, 23). Furthermore, certain low- and middle-income countries reported prevalence rates for asthma, rhinitis, and eczema symptoms that were comparable to some high-income Western countries. The core of this investigation was carried out in three phases. The first phase, which included more than 721,000 children and adolescents, revealed significant diversity in asthma prevalence (24). Considering only positive answers to the question "Have you ever had asthma"? Albania, Austria, Belgium, Estonia, Germany, India, Iran, Latvia, Poland, and Georgia had the lowest rates of childhood asthma (1.4 to 4.2%), while Australia, Costa Rica, and New Zealand had the highest rates (26.5 to 27.1%). Albania, Estonia, Ethiopia, Indonesia, Iran, Poland, Russia, South Korea, and Uzbekistan had low prevalence among adolescents (1.6-3%), while Australia, New Zealand, Oman, Peru, Singapore, and the United Kingdom had high prevalence (20.7 to 28.2%).

In a study of allergy and asthma epidemiology conducted in Spain, adolescents aged 13-14 years and schoolchildren aged 6-7 years had a prevalence of 15.3% and 10.4%, respectively. These values exceeded those of the ISAAC (10.6% in adolescents and 9.9% in schoolchildren) (25). The findings revealed a significant prevalence of asthmatic symptoms in teenagers, as well as a stabilization in Spanish students

in comparison to the ISAAC. Geographic variations in asthma prevalence are not well understood, however locations with high prevalence report large numbers to the Global Asthma Network (GAN) protocol.

According to several research, children with asthma are more likely to live in low-income households. The aforementioned Swedish study looked at the association between socioeconomic level, asthma, and rhinitis. Environmental factors, socioeconomic level (parental occupation), and symptoms of allergy illness at birth were assessed using questionnaires administered to children aged 1, 2, and 4. Blood samples from 2,614 4-year-old children were analyzed for specific IgE to common and dietary allergies. Asthma was shown to be more prevalent in lower socioeconomic categories than higher socioeconomic groups (26).

Other research (27) employ parental education level as a surrogate for socioeconomic position. They discovered that parental education had no direct effect on children's risk of acquiring an asthma diagnosis. However, they discovered an indirect relationship between the number of children in the family and the rate of overcrowding. Parents of lower socioeconomic class frequently engage in risky activities, such as smoking throughout pregnancy and continuing to do so afterward. On the other hand, parents with a high socioeconomic status appear to have a healthier lifestyle, which may avoid asthma.

Asthma is a diverse disease impacted by environmental factors such as weather and climate change, which vary in kind and severity across the globe. Climate change and air pollution are claimed to be associated with numerous symptoms of obstructive respiratory illnesses, such as asthma exacerbation, increased medication use, emergency department visits, and hospital admissions (5, 6). The rising incidence of respiratory disorders in recent years is thought to be due to a number of environmental factors, including increased levels of chemicals (particulate matter and gaseous components such as nitrogen dioxide and ozone) and biological triggers (aeroallergens). Several articles emphasize this (6, 7).

Throughout the 1990s, there was a growing interest in the role of environmental factors in asthma and allergies (6). The recent increase in the frequency of respiratory diseases is thought to be caused by a number of environmental changes, including an increase in the presence of chemicals (particulate matter and gaseous components such as nitrogen dioxide and ozone) and biological triggers (aeroallergens) (6, 7). Despite contradictory evidence, many people believe that climate change affects the production and dispersion of chemical and biological

components of air pollution. It raises the allergenic concentration of pollen and spores in the atmosphere, causing inflammation in the airways of allergy and asthma patients. Furthermore, based on the broad assumption that rising pollution and global warming produce an increase in allergy and asthma, it is widely considered that pollution-modified aeroallergens are more capable of triggering airway reactivity in allergic subjects, resulting in bronchial asthma symptoms (7).

Our findings in the instance of asthma show no significant differences in the total number of both sexes among asthmatics based on population. Furthermore, the lowest overall statistics (both sexes) are observed in populations with more than 400,000 inhabitants (3.95%), where increased pollution is assumed, whereas 4.48% in populations with less than 10,000 residents. The pattern remains consistent throughout multiple years of monitoring, with no substantial changes amongst populations, regardless of population size.

Conclusion

We have quantitative data from a 12-year series to back up the claim that asthma prevalence in Spain has been stable over the previous 12 years, and that higher prevalence is associated with social factors (older people, women, low income, and low education levels).

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